

Landscapes Have Distinct Emotion Profiles

Ioana E. Militaru^{a,b*}, Wijnand A.P. van Tilburg^c

^a Department of Psychology, University of Amsterdam, The Netherlands

^b Department of Psychology, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom

^c Department of Psychology, University of Essex, United Kingdom

Author Note

Ioana E. Militaru <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4856-1598>

Wijnand A.P. van Tilburg <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9724-0603>

Conflict of interest disclosure. The authors declared no potential conflict of interest with respect to the research.

Data Availability. An interactive dashboard accompanies this manuscript: Emotional Landscapes Explorer: <https://tinyurl.com/emotional-landscapes>

***Corresponding author:** Ioana Elisabeta Militaru, Department of Psychology, University of Amsterdam, Nieuwe Achtergracht 129-B, Amsterdam, 1018 WT, The Netherlands. Email: iem24@cantab.ac.uk

This preprint may be cited as:

Militaru, I.E., & Van Tilburg, W.A.P. (2025). *Landscapes have distinct emotion profiles* [Manuscript in preparation]

Abstract

Places fundamentally shape people's experiences: Contact with natural environments compared to artificial ones elicits positive emotions and dampens negative emotions. In the current study, we examine the link between landscapes and emotions at a more granular level than done before, differentiating between different types of natural and artificial landscapes, as well as between different emotions. We tested how 19 different landscape types related to 17 different emotions that participants rated (48,943 datapoints, nested within 192 participants). While multilevel analyses supported a soft nature-artificial dichotomy, whereby predominantly natural landscapes elicited overall more positive and less negative emotions compared to artificial landscapes, landscapes varied in their emotion profile. Coastal landscapes and forests had a homogeneously positive emotion profile, and heavily built landscapes had a homogeneously negative emotion profile. Yet, other landscapes showed heterogeneity in the specific emotions they elicited. These findings demonstrate that the link between landscapes and emotions is more nuanced than previously established and offers detailed insight into the emotion profile of landscapes. These results can inform psychological theory and can help planners, policy makers, and mental health practitioners build human-centric spaces.

Keywords: emotion, landscape, geography, nature, affect, environment

Landscapes Have Distinct Emotion Profiles

We are always *within* a landscape, natural or artificial, a park or a bustling city centre. The features and type of the landscapes we are in shape, at large scale and to varying degrees, our everyday thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. Perhaps unsurprisingly, natural, versus human-built, landscapes environments are lauded for their positive emotional impact (Wicks et al., 2022). This observation has been articulated in the ‘biophilia hypothesis’—the assumption that humans have an evolutionary meaningful connection to nature that, if satisfied, translates to a range of positive psychological outcomes (Kellert & Wilson, 1993). Research has supported this hypothesis; contact with natural environments, including parks and gardens, rivers and lakes, benefit a range of psychological outcomes, including general positive affect (Huynh et al., 2013), emotional wellbeing and happiness (Nisbet et al., 2011; Capaldi et al., 2014), relaxation (Park et al., 2007) and decreased boredom, loneliness, anger, fatigue, and anxiety (O’Dea et al., 2025; Astell-Burt et al., 2022; Bowler et al., 2010).

Landscapes and Emotions

Emotions have been studied in relation to a host of external triggers, ranging from specific objects placed within a larger context (e.g., Moynihan et al., 2015; Shiota et al., 2007), to broad situational contexts (Fahlman et al., 2013; Mercer-Lynn et al., 2014; Wildschut et al., 2006). The advent of geographical (Rentfrow, 2020), environmental (Craik, 1973), and socio-ecological (Oishi, 2014) psychological theories have called for ‘zooming-out’ perspectives of the physical environment, perspectives that take into account the influence of the broader features of the environment on psychological outcomes (Van de Vliert et al., 2023). Investigations into the influence of broad features of the environment, such as landscapes, climate, or topography, on psychological constructs are currently contributing to a burgeoning literature. Within this literature, nature has received notable

attention. Contact with the natural environment—broadly operationalised and measured—has been found to significantly and robustly increase a range of positive outcomes, from positive affect and cognitive function to blood pressure and sleep quality (e.g., Bratman et al., 2015; Capaldi et al., 2014; Jimenez et al., 2021).

In a strict sense, ‘nature’ is used to refer to physical features of landscapes that are not of human origin. Following on from this very definition, natural areas have generally been studied as being contrasting from artificial, human-made areas (Taylor et al., 2018; Vujcic et al., 2017). In practice, however, ‘natural’ environments have been subjectively defined; much of the extant research presents environments of human-made origin, such as gardens or parks, as being part of ‘nature’. The term ‘nature experience’ has been proposed to capture the very subjective evaluation of environmental features (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989).

Leaving terminological differences aside, the generally positive impact on psychological outcomes that nature seems to have over human-built environments warrants further evaluation. First, not all natural landscapes may elicit the same positive responses. For instance, visits to green landscapes (e.g., forests) seem to have longer lasting positive effects on wellbeing compared to blue landscapes (e.g., lakes; White et al., 2021). Differences emerge even across the same type of landscape. For instance, walking in a tended forest was found to increase positive affect to a larger degree compared to walking in a wild forest (Martens et al., 2011).

Second, when studying the short-term benefits of nature, emotions have been often considered as notable outcomes (Bowler et al., 2010), yet a significant amount of research has concentrated either on one single emotion (e.g., Astell-Burt et al., 2022; Huynh et al., 2013; MacKerron & Mourato, 2013), or on general positive or negative affect (Bowler et al., 2010). Advancements in emotion theorising proposed that emotion categories (e.g., awe, boredom) better organise emotion experience and recognition compared to general positive

versus negative affect (Cowen & Keltner, 2017). We seek to apply this perspective to the psychology of landscapes by systematically testing whether granular types of landscapes evoke different emotions to different degrees.

Why Would Landscapes Elicit Emotions?

Landscapes can impact emotion intensity through several routes. First, nature is restorative. The attention restoration theory posits that people escape from physical and social stressors by effortlessly paying attention to the ‘soft fascinations’ encountered in the natural world (Home et al., 2012; Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989). Indeed, nature was found to inspire appreciation for its beautiful scenery and, in turn, it leads to increased aesthetic valuations (Anderson et al., 2018; Farzanfar & Walther, 2023). In another complementary account of nature’s restorative effects, the psycho-evolutionary theory put forward by Ulrich and colleagues proposed that contact with nature allows for psychophysiological stress recovery through the attributes of the natural environment such as spatial openness, the presence of diverse patterns, or water features. In turn, attending to these features rapidly elicits positive and blocks negative affect by decreasing physiological activation (Ulrich, 1983; Ulrich et al., 1991). To date, evidence for the restorative effects of nature is thought to be generally strong. A systematic review of the evidence concluded that nature indeed effectively reduces self-reported anger, fatigue, anxiety, and sadness, whilst increasing energy levels and attention (Bowler et al., 2010), providing strong support for nature’s palliative role. There is good reason to believe that landscapes elicit emotions as they can restore and reduce stress levels.

The above ‘restoration account’ of natural (vs human-built) environments thus suggests broad differences in nature vs human-built landscapes, with natural ones leading to comparatively more positive outcomes (e.g., more intense positive emotions, less intense negative emotions), but is mostly silent about potential differences in the impact of landscapes within these two categories.

A second route through which landscapes may shape emotions is through their basic composition. At a granular level of analysis, landscapes hold visual properties that impact attention engagement. Colors and patterns that are more complex, diverse or intense—like those found in several natural landscapes—are preferred. For example, landscapes’ visual complexity, measured as fractal dimension, plays a role in our scene preference (Hagerhall et al., 2004). Higher levels of brightness and saturation are also found to be attention-grabbing. In one experiment, Camgöz and colleagues (2004) found that colors high in saturation and brightness increased levels of attention. In turn, focusing attention was found to increase the perception of saturation (Carrasco et al., 2004; Fuller & Carrasco, 2006), signalling a potential feedback loop between visual characteristics of landscapes and attention. The specific colors present in landscapes are also likely to impact specific emotions. Elsadek and colleagues (2014; 2017), for example, that green bright green and yellow foliage elicited feelings of relaxation, comfort, cheerfulness, and calm, when compared to natural foliage that was predominantly (dark) red or white. Specific emotions were also found to be sensitive to changes in the visual properties of landscapes. For instance, images of artificial landscapes were manipulated to look brighter, more saturated, or higher in contrast elicit lower levels of boredom compared to the same images low on these visual properties (O’Dea et al., 2025). Different from the restoration account, whether a landscape is natural or human-built does not necessarily matter in this respect; what matters are their compositional properties, albeit that those may systematically differ between the natural or human-built categories (Le et al., 2017; Wilkins et al., 2018). Accordingly, differences in the psychological impact of landscapes can be expected when those landscapes differ in compositional features, even if they belong to the same parent ‘nature’ or ‘human-built’ category.

Current Study

Unlike other emotion elicitors, landscapes can increase, dampen, modify or elicit emotional states anywhere we go. The ubiquity of the relationship between landscapes and emotions begs questioning: Do all natural landscapes elicit positive emotions versus negative emotions relative to human-built landscapes? Are there different compositions in the specific emotions that landscapes elicit, with, for example, some landscapes eliciting positive emotions across the board, and other eliciting a select few only? In the present investigation, we set out to examine the emotion profile of landscapes at a granular level, both in terms of landscapes and specific emotions, addressing recent calls for systematic enquiry into landscapes' psychological outcomes (Braubach et al., 2021).

We aim to identify which specific emotions are elicited by different types of landscapes, both when comparing broad natural versus human-built groups and when zeroing in on specific landscape types within these categories. Accordingly, we set out to investigate whether in addition to general differences in emotion profile of landscapes according to a nature-artificial dichotomy, further differences exist between landscape categories beyond this dichotomy (e.g., comparing forests, coastal or residential landscapes).

To comprehensively examine the emotion profile of landscapes, we made use of two classification: the land cover taxonomy (Anderson, 1976), and the circumplex model of emotions (Posner et al., 2005). To operationalise landscapes we used a variation of a land cover taxonomy that has been widely used in the geographical literature (Anderson, 1976) and that differentiates between 19 types of landscapes: (1) coast, (2) woodlands: coniferous, (3) woodlands: deciduous, (4) heath, (5) wetlands, (6) agricultural: orchards, (7) agricultural: crops, (8) agricultural: mixed, (9) farm, (10) glasshouse, (11) recreational land, (12) recreational building, (13) residential: low density, (14) residential: medium density, (15) residential: high density, (16) industry: business parks, (17) industry: retail park, (18) industry: industrial area, (19) railroad. We used the Southampton-York Natural Scenes

(SYNS) dataset to create the bank of stimuli (Adams et al., 2016). The SYNS dataset contains high-resolution images of the 19 types of landscapes.

Second, we used the circumplex model of emotions, a widely used theoretical framework in the emotion literature, to guide our selection of emotion terms included in the study (Posner, Russell, & Peterson, 2005). To their 15 emotion terms captured by the circumplex model we added—“nostalgia” and “awe”—due to their recently uncovered links to external and natural stimuli. Nostalgia has been repeatedly shown to be elicited by external stimuli, including by natural environments (Militaru et al., 2025), locations, objects (Wildschut et al., 2006), scents (Reid et al., 2015), extreme weather (Van Tilburg et al., 2018), and natural environments (Militaru et al., 2025). Among the various elicitors of awe—an emotional response to overwhelmingly vast stimuli—‘nature’ featured as the most frequent when participants were asked to retrospectively describe an event in which they felt this emotion (Shiota et al., 2007).

Method

Participants and Design

We recruited 200 UK-based participants who completed the study. Data collection took place over 7 days, and participants were recruited through the Prolific platform ($n = 160$) and via the University of Essex psychology department’s research participation system, SONA ($n = 46$). Prolific Participants were compensated £2.50 for taking part in the study, and SONA participants received course credit. We excluded participants who did not complete the entire survey, leaving a final sample of 192 participants, out of which 68.75% self-identified as female, 30.21% as male and 1.05% as non-binary (age [18-78], $M = 35.94$, $SD = 15.58$).

Materials and Procedure

After informed consent was obtained, participants were presented with 15 randomly selected images from the bank of 75 scenes that forms the Southampton-York Natural Scenes (SYNS; Adams et al., 2016) dataset¹ (Figure 1). The SYNS dataset features images of outdoor landscapes, corresponding to the 19 landscape categories (see Supplement Table S1 for a detailed description of each category). For each landscape category, the developers randomly selected locations within 40km of the University of Southampton campus in Hampshire, UK (for a full methodology please refer to Adams et al., 2016). The high-resolution stereo scans of the SYNS dataset are useful in creating depth and the appearance of three dimensions. For the present study, we used the stereo pairs to create panoramic images to mimic the impression of a larger landscape with Adobe Lightroom, producing 2048 px by 674 px resolution images.

Each image that participants viewed in our study was followed by 17 emotions presented in random order after the stem: “When looking at this landscape do you feel:” (1) "nostalgic", (2) "awe", (3) "elated", (4) "happy", (5) "excited", (6) "serene", (7) "calm", (8) "contented", (9) "relaxed", (10) "bored", (11) "alert", (12) "tense", (13) "nervous", (14) "upset", (15) "stressed", (16) "sad", (17) "depressed.” Response scales for the 17 emotion words ranged from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 7 (*strongly agree*), and were then standardized. Demographics questions (i.e., gender, age) and debriefing concluded the study.

¹ Note that their dataset contains an additional 76th image which we did not use due to compression issues.

A. Coast

B. Woodlands: Coniferous

C. Residential: High Density

Figure 1. Examples of mini-panoramic images corresponding to three landscape categories represented in the SYNS dataset.

Results

Emotions in Response to Landscapes

We first tested the prediction that natural versus human-built landscapes elicit more intense positive emotion and less intense negative emotions. To this end, emotion intensity was entered as dependent variable in a multilevel analysis, with a random intercept allocated to participants. Emotion type (sad, stressed, nervous etc.) was entered as fixed-effect predictor, as was parent landscape category (natural vs human-built). We also entered the

emotion type \times parent landscape interaction. Significance levels were estimated using Satterthwaite approximation (Luke, 2017). This analysis produced a significant interaction, indicating that differences in emotion intensity when comparing natural and human-built landscapes varied by emotion $F(16; 48,718) = 467.17, p < .001$.

We therefore estimated marginal means (Figure 2) and corresponding 95% confidence intervals for natural and human-built landscapes separately for each of the 17 emotions. As predicted, natural landscapes presented an overall positive emotion profile, with every positive emotion being more intense for natural than human-built landscapes, and every negative emotion less intense for natural versus human-built landscapes, with alertness being the only exception.

Next, we tested if, beyond these differences in natural and human-built environments, there was variability in the emotion profiles of specific landscape types. We estimate a similar multilevel model but replaced parent landscape category by the specific landscapes (coast, coniferous woodlands, deciduous woodlands etc.). The interaction between landscape and emotion type was again significant, $F(288; 48,429) = 45.53, p < .001$, indicating that the specific configuration of elicited emotions varied by landscape. Figure 3 displays the estimated marginal means for each emotion and landscape pairing; further details, including 95% confidence intervals, are listed in Supplement Table S2.

Figure 2. Estimated marginal means for emotions’ intensity for the two parent categories: A. Human-built and B. Natural Landscapes.

Across these results, landscapes presented a distinct emotion profile, eliciting varying degrees of both positive and negative emotions. An interactive dashboard of these results can be found here: <https://tinyurl.com/emotional-landscapes>.

Coastal areas elicited strong positive emotions, such as nostalgia, awe, elation, happiness, excitement, alertness, serenity, calmness, contentment, and relaxation. Deciduous and coniferous woodlands similarly led to increased levels of positive emotions, such as awe, elation, happiness, excitement, alertness, serenity, and contentment. Coastal areas along with forests (deciduous and coniferous) led to lower intensities for all negative emotions. The emotion profile of the remaining natural landscapes appeared to be more complex, marked by differences even within apparently similar categories. Heaths, wetlands, crops, and orchards—all landscapes containing predominantly natural elements—were associated with higher

intensities of some positive emotions, such as nostalgia, relaxation, calmness, or happiness and lower intensities of some negative emotions, such as feeling tense, bored, or stressed.

Negative emotions, such as stress, nervousness, tension, and sometimes boredom, were strongest in intensity in response to heavily artificial landscapes, which included recreational buildings, high density residential areas, retail parks, industrial areas, and railroads. Conversely, heavily artificial landscapes featured a comparative reduction in positive emotions such as relaxation, contentment, calmness, serenity, excitement, happiness, elation, awe, or nostalgia. Certain landscapes that are arguably human made, such as recreational buildings, farms, and low-density residential areas did not elicit negative emotions. In sum, heavily built artificial landscapes robustly elicited strong negative emotions, yet the same emotion profile does not generalise to all artificial landscapes.

Figure 3. Estimates from the multilevel model for emotion and landscape categories in predicting emotion intensity. Blue colours represent positive estimates, and red colours represent negative estimates. Significant estimates ($p < .05$, $p < .01$, or $p < .001$) are represented with a square, and non-significant estimate are represented with a circle.

Discussion

We set out to identify what emotions different landscapes elicit by asking participants to rate the intensity of felt emotions using 17 emotion terms in response to scenes of landscapes corresponding to 19 landscape categories. The results were generally supportive of a soft nature-artificial dichotomy: Vegetation and nature-dense landscapes, such as coasts or forests, elicited predominantly positive emotions. Landscapes made up of heavily built structures, such as industrial or retail parks predominantly elicited predominantly negative emotions. However, heterogeneity appeared to be the norm rather than the exception: Several landscapes evoked distinct patterns of negative and positive emotions.

Natural Landscapes and Emotions

Coasts. Scenes of coastal landscapes led participants to report an increased intensity across all positive emotions, from awe and nostalgia to serenity and contentment. Participants reported lower levels for all negative emotions, such as boredom, sadness or nervousness, in response to scenes of coastal landscapes. These results are aligned with prior findings. For example, White and colleagues (2013) found that, in the UK, proximity to the coast is associated with higher levels of happiness, life satisfaction, and mental health. The positive impact of coastal areas on a psychological outcomes has been found to be robust (White et al., 2020, 2021), but the same effect seems to generalise to inland waters, such as rivers and lakes. Living near inland water bodies was found to be associated with better mental health outcomes, such as lower rates of anxiety and mood disorder hospitalisations (Pearson et al., 2019), better self-reported health, and lower levels of anxiety and depression (Garrett et al., 2019). Extant literature has repeatedly confirmed that blue landscapes—those encompassing bodies of water, such as lakes, rivers, or coastal areas—can influence emotions (Militaru et al., 2025; Igou & Van Tilburg, 2019), behaviours, and wellbeing (Braubach et al., 2021) for the better.

Regardless, the present findings beg questioning: Why would coastal areas lead to such a robust increase in positive emotions? Elements of coastal scenes, such as a beach sunset, elicit aesthetic responses (i.e., a sense of beauty) due to their contour properties (Farzanfar & Walther, 2023). Prior research supports this hypothesis. Landscapes' levels of complexity, measured through the landscapes' fractal dimension, plays a role in our preference for nature. Scenes that encompass both water bodies and vegetation have fractal properties that people tend to prefer (Hagerhall et al., 2004; Taylor et al., 2011). Placed in context of our current finding, fractal properties of coastal scenes may be the fodder of positive emotions.

Deciduous and Coniferous Woodlands

Both deciduous and coniferous woodlands led to increased intensities in all positive emotions, such as awe, elation, happiness, excitement, alertness, serenity, and contentment, and to lower levels of negative emotions, from boredom to sadness and nervousness. However, notable differences exist in the estimated marginal means, with deciduous woodlands leading to higher increases in positive emotions than coniferous woodlands.

Overall, the emotion profile of forests emerging in this study adds to the pool of evidence suggesting that exposure to forests leads to improved emotion outcomes. For example, Bielinis and colleagues (2019) found that a 15-minute exposure to snow-covered forests decreased negative affect, anxiety, anger, and fatigue compared to urban landscapes. To these findings, we add a distinction between deciduous forests, comprised of trees that shed foliage with seasonal change, and evergreen, coniferous forests. While both decreased negative emotions, only deciduous forests inspired stronger positive emotions.

Wetlands and Heaths

Wetlands and heaths, two other landscapes containing predominantly natural elements, were associated with higher intensities of some positive emotions, such as

contentment, relaxation, calmness, or happiness, but not nostalgia. Recent findings uncovered a rather unique psychology of wetlands and heaths (Militaru et al., 2024). Wetlands are landscapes that generally encompass wet meadows and low vegetation, while heaths are landscapes characterised by low scrubby vegetation, low grass, or moss. Arguably, wetlands and heaths have distinct geographical characteristics which offer little opportunity for human-environment interactions and, consequently, may differently relate to psychological states. Indeed, heaths and wetlands appear to have a less homogenous emotion profile compared to other natural landscapes, such as coastal areas or forests.

Recreational Landscapes

Recreational lands, encompassing areas such as recreational parks, sport fields or botanical gardens, with large areas of manicured grass land, elicited an increase in all positive emotions, with the largest positive increase in levels of nostalgia and relaxation. Recreational lands are also decreasing some, but not all, negative emotions: While tension and boredom levels are significantly lower in response to these landscapes, levels of sadness were not influenced by them. The diverse profile of this landscape may be explained by the diverse functions they fulfil: Botanical gardens have very different functions compared to sport fields which may, in turn, influence the associated emotion.

Agricultural Landscapes

Agricultural landscapes where natural and human-made elements are mixed, such as farms and orchards, had a relatively mixed emotion profile. Specifically, participants rated orchards as leading to little or no change in the intensity of emotions², apart from a notable decrease in boredom. Farms, mixed agricultural landscapes and crops in turn increased all positive emotions, including relaxation, calmness, and serenity, and decreased all negative

² Neutral emotion profiles were characterized by a lack of significance in their association with emotion intensity.

emotions. Agricultural lands are a notable example of mixed natural and human-made lands; while the natural elements of agricultural landscapes encourage a deeper connection with the natural world and its resources, their artificial elements act as a reminder of humans' environmental impact (Riechers et al., 2019), which were found to have a positive impact on emotions. These results suggest that the nature-human-made dichotomy does not fully represent the emotion profile of landscapes; landscape types have distinct emotion profiles.

Human-made Landscapes and Emotions

Human-made landscapes generally lead to an increase in negative emotions. Nonetheless, as for natural landscapes, the emotion profile of human-made landscapes was heterogenous, with heavily built artificial landscapes presenting a negative emotion profile, while other, less built, artificial areas presented a more positive emotion profile.

Industrial Areas, Railroads, Recreational Buildings

Railroads and industrial areas (retail parks and general industrial areas) had a predominantly negative emotion profile, leading to higher levels of stress, nervousness, tension, and boredom, while being largely incompatible with positive emotions. Scenes of business parks, encompassing large modern constructions increased all negative emotions and decreased all positive emotions. Similarly, scenes of recreational buildings, encompassing hospitals, university campuses or exhibition halls, elicited negative emotions and reduced positive ones. Prior research offered converging evidence. Residents of areas encompassing large constructions, such as motorways or large industrial buildings, tend to report reduced mental wellbeing compared to those who live further away (Foley et al., 2017; Krefis et al., 2018).

Residential Areas

Residential areas, encompassing areas with low-density buildings (i.e., smaller, 1-2 storey buildings with large areas of vegetation), medium-density buildings (i.e., 3-5 storey

buildings with some areas of vegetation), and high-density buildings (i.e., more than 3 storey buildings with little vegetation) had a mixed emotion profile. Participants reported feeling more bored but also less awe when looking at scenes of low-density residential areas. Participants rated scenes of medium density residential areas as being incompatible with all positive emotions. Medium density residential areas increased feelings of boredom, sadness and depression, but did not reduce stress or nervousness. In contrast, high-density residential areas were rated as being conducive of all negative emotions, while being incompatible with all positive emotions. Overall, these results suggest that residential areas are notably distinct in their emotion profiles: Areas that have a mixture of human-built and natural elements have positive emotion profiles. Previous studies offered support for this finding. Green spaces such as gardens or allotments found in urban places were found to mitigate the stress incurred by residents of urban areas (Krefis et al., 2018; Ward Thompson et al., 2016).

Taken together, we found that heavily built landscapes had a predominantly negative emotion profile, eliciting emotions such as stress, nervousness, and tension. Contrastingly, residential areas varied significantly in their emotion profile, with low-density residential areas having a predominantly positive emotion profile.

Implications

Landscapes are omnipresent: We are always *within* a landscape, and, in turn, our thoughts, feelings, and behaviors can be shaped, influenced, or elicited by features of the landscape we are in (MacKerron & Mourato, 2013, Rentfrow et al., 2008). Landscapes act as a canvas to a range of human activity: The walkability of an urban landscape can shape our behavior, biodiversity can shape our emotions, and population density can shape our social interactions (Militaru et al., 2024).

Comprehensively studying the psychological effects of landscapes is no small feat, due to the sheer variety of methodological approaches and landscape taxonomies. Previous

studies have tested the effect of natural stimuli using real-life exposure to nature (Bowler et al., 2010), lab exposure to specific features of nature (Elsadek et al., 2017; Elsadek & Fujii, 2014), virtual nature (Gao et al., 2019; Valtchanov et al., 2010), or even by measuring proximity to a window view of nature (Sharam et al., 2023; Soga et al., 2021). In extension, extant research has largely concentrated on landscapes that are typically embedded in urban settings (e.g., parks, gardens), or that individuals are inadvertently exposed to (e.g., urban areas). In the present study, we applied a widely used taxonomy in geographical sciences to systematically explore the emotion profile of landscapes. We found that from 19 categories of landscapes, 8 landscape, including residential areas, orchards, heaths, and wetlands, had a heterogenous emotion profile. Our results suggest that individuals construe landscapes in a way that is compatible with a soft nature-human-made dichotomy. These findings can be leveraged by urban planners to improve accessibility to coastal areas or deciduous forests in an effort to emphasise the wellbeing implications of changing landscapes (e.g., Taylor et al., 2018; Vujcic et al., 2017).

Limitations

It is important to clarify that we do not propose that the emotion profile of landscapes emerging in the present study is a perfect estimate of lived experiences. There are elements of experiencing nature, such as sounds, smells, and activities, that are not captured by photographic stimuli such as the ones used in the current study. Colours were found to partly account for humans' biophilic tendencies. Natural scenes, containing more green and blue hues, were previously found to be more scenic than grey scenes containing human-made structures. In turn, those living in more scenic areas report better health (Seresinhe et al., 2015). Sounds found in nature were also shown to lead to restorative effects (Alvarsson et al., 2010). It is plausible that natural smells play a similar role and contribute to nature's palliative role (Anandakumar et al., 2021). Future studies would benefit from including

reports of lived experiences of different landscapes, along with their relevant physical properties.

We additionally note that, while our landscape taxonomy included 19 categories, certain landscapes, such as mountains or deserts, were not represented in this study's set of stimuli. Future research should consider using photographic stimuli extracted from other geographical regions.

3.4.4 Conclusion

The present study shows that landscapes differ in the emotions they elicit. Natural landscapes, particularly coasts and deciduous forests, had a consistently positive emotion profile, increasing awe and nostalgia, and decreasing boredom and stress, yet this effect is not present across all natural landscapes. Conversely, while human-made landscapes presented a negative emotion profile, farms and low-residential areas were predominantly positively laden. These findings suggest that the emotion profile of landscapes is compatible with a soft natural-human-built dichotomy but cannot be reduced to it. We find that each landscape holds specific emotion qualities. In the context of rapid urban expansion and environmental change, recognising the nuanced emotional value of different landscapes is essential for designing and managing places that support human wellbeing.

References

- Adams, W. J., Elder, J. H., Graf, E. W., Leyland, J., Lugtigheid, A. J., & Muryy, A. (2016). The Southampton-York Natural Scenes (SYNS) dataset: Statistics of surface attitude. *Scientific Reports*, 6(1), 35805.
- Alvarsson, J. J., Wiens, S., & Nilsson, M. E. (2010). Stress recovery during exposure to nature sound and environmental noise. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 7(3), 1036–1046.

- Anandakumar, P., Kamaraj, S., & Vanitha, M. K. (2021). D-limonene: A multifunctional compound with potent therapeutic effects. *Journal of Food Biochemistry*, *45*(1), e13566.
- Anderson, C. L., Monroy, M., & Keltner, D. (2018). Awe in nature heals: Evidence from military veterans, at-risk youth, and college students. *Emotion*, *18*(8), 1195–1202. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0019006>
- Anderson, J. R. (1976). *A land use and land cover classification system for use with remote sensor data* (Vol. 964). US Government Printing Office.
- Astell-Burt, T., Hartig, T., Eckermann, S., Nieuwenhuijsen, M., McMunn, A., Frumkin, H., & Feng, X. (2022). More green, less lonely? A longitudinal cohort study. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, *51*(1), 99–110.
- Bielinis, E., Łukowski, A., Omelan, A., Boiko, S., Takayama, N., & Grebner, D. L. (2019). The effect of recreation in a snow-covered forest environment on the psychological wellbeing of young adults: Randomized controlled study. *Forests*, *10*(10), 827.
- Bowler, D. E., Buyung-Ali, L. M., Knight, T. M., & Pullin, A. S. (2010). A systematic review of evidence for the added benefits to health of exposure to natural environments. *BMC Public Health*, *10*(1), 1–10.
- Bratman, G. N., Hamilton, J. P., Hahn, K. S., Daily, G. C., & Gross, J. J. (2015). Nature experience reduces rumination and subgenual prefrontal cortex activation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *112*(28), 8567–8572.
- Braubach, M., Kendrovski, V., Jarosinska, D., Mudu, P., Andreucci, M. B., Beute, F., Davies, Z., de Vries, S., Glanville, J., & Keune, H. (2021). *Green and blue spaces and mental health: New evidence and perspectives for action*.

- Camgöz, N., Yener, C., & Güvenç, D. (2002). Effects of hue, saturation, and brightness on preference. *Color Research & Application*, 27(3), 199-207.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/col.10214>
- Capaldi, C. A., Dopko, R. L., & Zelenski, J. M. (2014). The relationship between nature connectedness and happiness: A meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 5*Music-evoked nostalgia: Affect, memory, and personality.*, 976.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.00976>
- Carrasco, M., Ling, S., & Read, S. (2004). Attention alters appearance. *Nature Neuroscience*, 7(3), 308–313. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn1194>
- Cowen, A. S., & Keltner, D. (2017). Self-report captures 27 distinct categories of emotion bridged by continuous gradients. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(38), E7900–E7909.
- Craik, K. H. (1973). Environmental psychology. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 24(1), 403–422.
- Donovan, G. H., Butry, D. T., Michael, Y. L., Prestemon, J. P., Liebhold, A. M., Gatzliolis, D., & Mao, M. Y. (2013). The relationship between trees and human health: Evidence from the spread of the emerald ash borer. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 44(2), 139–145.
- Elsadek, M., & Fujii, E. (2014). People’s psycho-physiological responses to plantscape colors stimuli: A pilot study. *Int. J. Psychol. Behav. Sci*, 4, 70–78.
- Elsadek, M., & Fujii, E. (2014). People’s psycho-physiological responses to plantscape colors stimuli: A pilot study. *Int. J. Psychol. Behav. Sci*, 4, 70-78.
- Elsadek, M., Sun, M., & Fujii, E. (2017). Psycho-physiological responses to plant variegation as measured through eye movement, self-reported emotion and cerebral activity. *Indoor and Built Environment*, 26(6), 758–770.

- Elsadek, M., Sun, M., & Fujii, E. (2017). Psycho-physiological responses to plant variegation as measured through eye movement, self-reported emotion and cerebral activity. *Indoor and Built Environment*, 26(6), 758-770.
- Fahlman, S. A., Mercer-Lynn, K. B., Flora, D. B., & Eastwood, J. D. (2013). Development and validation of the multidimensional state boredom scale. *Assessment*, 20(1), 68–85.
- Farzanfar, D., & Walther, D. B. (2023). Changing what you like: Modifying contour properties shifts aesthetic valuations of scenes. *Psychological Science*, 34(10), 1101–1120.
- Foley, L., Prins, R., Crawford, F., Humphreys, D., Mitchell, R., Sahlqvist, S., Thomson, H., Ogilvie, D., & M74 Study Team. (2017). Effects of living near an urban motorway on the wellbeing of local residents in deprived areas: Natural experimental study. *Plos One*, 12(4), e0174882.
- Fuller, S., & Carrasco, M. (2006). Exogenous attention and color perception: Performance and appearance of saturation and hue. *Vision Research*, 46(23), 4032–4047.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.visres.2006.07.014>
- Gao, T., Zhang, T., Zhu, L., Gao, Y., & Qiu, L. (2019). Exploring psychophysiological restoration and individual preference in the different environments based on virtual reality. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(17), 3102.
- Garrett, J. K., Clitherow, T. J., White, M. P., Wheeler, B. W., & Fleming, L. E. (2019). Coastal proximity and mental health among urban adults in England: The moderating effect of household income. *Health & Place*, 59, 102200.
- Hagerhall, C. M., Purcell, T., & Taylor, R. (2004). Fractal dimension of landscape silhouette outlines as a predictor of landscape preference. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 24(2), 247–255.

- Home, R., Hunziker, M., & Bauer, N. (2012). Psychosocial outcomes as motivations for visiting nearby urban green spaces. *Leisure Sciences*, 34(4), 350–365.
- Huynh, Q., Craig, W., Janssen, I., & Pickett, W. (2013). Exposure to public natural space as a protective factor for emotional well-being among young people in Canada. *BMC Public Health*, 13(1), 1–14.
- Igou, E. R., & van Tilburg, W. A. (2019). A remedy for boredom: Natural environments as a psychological resource. In *Physical Activity in Natural Settings* (pp. 152-161). Routledge.
- Jimenez, M. P., DeVille, N. V., Elliott, E. G., Schiff, J. E., Wilt, G. E., Hart, J. E., & James, P. (2021). Associations between nature exposure and health: A review of the evidence. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(9), 4790.
- Kaplan, R., & Kaplan, S. (1989). *The experience of nature: A psychological perspective*. Cambridge university press.
- Kellert, S. R., & Wilson, E. O. (1993). *The biophilia hypothesis*. Island press.
- Krefis, A. C., Augustin, M., Schlünzen, K. H., Oßenbrügge, J., & Augustin, J. (2018). How does the urban environment affect health and well-being? A systematic review. *Urban Science*, 2(1), 21.
- Le, A. T., Payne, J., Clarke, C., Kelly, M. A., Prudenziati, F., Armsby, E., ... & Wilkins, A. J. (2017). Discomfort from urban scenes: Metabolic consequences. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 160, 61-68.
- Luke, S. G. (2017). Evaluating significance in linear mixed-effects models in R. *Behavior Research Methods*, 49(4), 1494-1502.
- MacKerron, G., & Mourato, S. (2013). Happiness is greater in natural environments. *Global Environmental Change*, 23(5), 992–1000.

- Martens, D., Gutscher, H., & Bauer, N. (2011). Walking in “wild” and “tended” urban forests: The impact on psychological well-being. *Journal of Environmental Psychology, 31*(1), 36–44.
- Mercer-Lynn, K. B., Bar, R. J., & Eastwood, J. D. (2014). Causes of boredom: The person, the situation, or both? *Personality and Individual Differences, 56*, 122–126.
- Militaru, I. E., Serapio-García, G., Ebert, T., Kong, W., Gosling, S. D., Potter, J., ... & Götz, F. M. (2024). The lay of the land: Associations between environmental features and personality. *Journal of Personality, 92*(1), 88-110. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jopy.12822>
- Militaru, I. E., Van Tilburg, W. A. P., Sedikides, C., Wildschut, T., & Rentfrow, P. J. (2025). Searching for Ithaca: The geography and psychological benefits of nostalgic places. *Current Research in Ecological and Social Psychology, 100223*.
- Moynihan, A. B., Van Tilburg, W. A. P., Igou, E. R., Wisman, A., Donnelly, A. E., & Mulcaire, J. B. (2015). Eaten up by boredom: Consuming food to escape awareness of the bored self. *Frontiers in Psychology, 6*, 369.
- Nakagawa, S., & Schielzeth, H. (2013). A general and simple method for obtaining R² from generalized linear mixed-effects models. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution, 4*(2), 133–142.
- Nisbet, E. K., Zelenski, J. M., & Murphy, S. A. (2011). Happiness is in our nature: Exploring nature relatedness as a contributor to subjective well-being. *Journal of Happiness Studies, 12*, 303–322.
- O'Dea, M. K., Militaru, I. E., Igou, E. R., Rentfrow, P. J., Barrett, I., & Van Tilburg, W. A. P. (2025). Nature adds color to life: Less boredom in natural versus artificial environments. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0001764>
- Oishi, S. (2014). Socioecological psychology. *Annual Review of Psychology, 65*, 581–609.

- Park, B.-J., Tsunetsugu, Y., Kasetani, T., Hirano, H., Kagawa, T., Sato, M., & Miyazaki, Y. (2007). Physiological effects of shinrin-yoku (taking in the atmosphere of the forest)—Using salivary cortisol and cerebral activity as indicators. *Journal of Physiological Anthropology*, *26*(2), 123–128.
- Pearson, A. L., Shortridge, A., Delamater, P. L., Horton, T. H., Dahlin, K., Rzotkiewicz, A., & Marchiori, M. J. (2019). Effects of freshwater blue spaces may be beneficial for mental health: A first, ecological study in the North American Great Lakes region. *PloS One*, *14*(8), e0221977.
- Posner, J., Russell, J. A., & Peterson, B. S. (2005). The circumplex model of affect: An integrative approach to affective neuroscience, cognitive development, and psychopathology. *Development and Psychopathology*, *17*(3), 715–734.
- Reid, C. A., Green, J. D., Wildschut, T., & Sedikides, C. (2015). Scent-evoked nostalgia. *Memory*, *23*(2), 157–166. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09658211.2013.876048>
- Rentfrow, P. J. (2020). Geographical psychology. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, *32*, 165–170.
- Rentfrow, P. J., Gosling, S. D., & Potter, J. (2008). A theory of the emergence, persistence, and expression of geographic variation in psychological characteristics. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, *3*(5), 339-369.
- Riechers, M., Henkel, W., Engbers, M., & Fischer, J. (2019). Stories of favourite places in public spaces: Emotional responses to landscape change. *Sustainability*, *11*(14), 3851.
- Seresinhe, C. I., Preis, T., & Moat, H. S. (2015). Quantifying the impact of scenic environments on health. *Scientific Reports*, *5*(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep16899>

- Sharam, L., Mayer, K., & Baumann, O. (2023). Design by nature: The influence of windows on cognitive performance and affect. *Journal of Environmental Psychology, 85*, 101923.
- Shiota, M. N., Keltner, D., & Mossman, A. (2007). The nature of awe: Elicitors, appraisals, and effects on self-concept. *COGNITION AND EMOTION, 21*(5), 944–963.
- Soga, M., Evans, M. J., Tsuchiya, K., & Fukano, Y. (2021). A room with a green view: The importance of nearby nature for mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Ecological Applications, 31*(2), e2248.
- Sugiyama, T., Leslie, E., Giles-Corti, B., & Owen, N. (2008). Associations of neighbourhood greenness with physical and mental health: Do walking, social coherence and local social interaction explain the relationships? *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health, 62*(5), ARTN-e9.
- Taylor, L., Hahs, A. K., & Hochuli, D. F. (2018). Wellbeing and urban living: Nurtured by nature. *Urban Ecosystems, 21*, 197–208.
- Taylor, R. P., Spehar, B., Van Donkelaar, P., & Hagerhall, C. M. (2011). Perceptual and physiological responses to Jackson Pollock's fractals. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience, 5*, 60.
- Ulrich, R. S. (1983). Aesthetic and affective response to natural environment. In *Behavior and the natural environment* (pp. 85–125). Springer.
- Ulrich, R. S., Simons, R. F., Losito, B. D., Fiorito, E., Miles, M. A., & Zelson, M. (1991). Stress recovery during exposure to natural and urban environments. *Journal of Environmental Psychology, 11*(3), 201–230.
- Valtchanov, D., Barton, K. R., & Ellard, C. (2010). Restorative effects of virtual nature settings. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking, 13*(5), 503–512.

- Van de Vliert, E., Conway III, L. G., & Van Lange, P. A. (2023). Enriching psychology by zooming out to general mindsets and practices in natural habitats. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 17456916221141657.
- Van Tilburg, W. A. P., Sedikides, C., & Wildschut, T. (2018). Adverse weather evokes nostalgia. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 44(7), 984–995.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167218756030>
- Vujcic, M., Tomicevic-Dubljevic, J., Grbic, M., Lecic-Tosevski, D., Vukovic, O., & Toskovic, O. (2017). Nature based solution for improving mental health and well-being in urban areas. *Environmental Research*, 158, 385–392.
- Ward Thompson, C., Aspinall, P., Roe, J., Robertson, L., & Miller, D. (2016). Mitigating stress and supporting health in deprived urban communities: The importance of green space and the social environment. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 13(4), 440.
- White, M. P., Alcock, I., Wheeler, B. W., & Depledge, M. H. (2013). Coastal proximity, health and well-being: Results from a longitudinal panel survey. *Health & Place*, 23, 97–103.
- White, M. P., Elliott, L. R., Gascon, M., Roberts, B., & Fleming, L. E. (2020). Blue space, health and well-being: A narrative overview and synthesis of potential benefits. *Environmental Research*, 191, 110169.
- White, M. P., Elliott, L. R., Grellier, J., Economou, T., Bell, S., Bratman, G. N., Cirach, M., Gascon, M., Lima, M. L., & Löhmus, M. (2021). Associations between green/blue spaces and mental health across 18 countries. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 8903.
- Wicks, C., Barton, J., Orbell, S., & Andrews, L. (2022). Psychological benefits of outdoor physical activity in natural versus urban environments: A systematic review and meta-

analysis of experimental studies. *Applied Psychology: Health and Well-Being*, 14(3), 1037-1061.

Wildschut, T., Sedikides, C., Arndt, J., & Routledge, C. (2006). Nostalgia: Content, triggers, functions. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 91(5), 975–993.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.91.5.975>

Wilkins, A. J., Penacchio, O., & Leonards, U. (2018). The built environment and its patterns: a view from the vision sciences. *Journal of Sustainable Design and Applied Research in Innovative Engineering of the Built Environment*

Supplementary Material

Table S1

Detailed description of land cover categories as presented in the Southampton-York Natural Scenes dataset

Category	Description	Parent Category
Coast	Sand dunes, including those with some marram grass covering, and un-washed beaches.	Natural
Woodlands: Coniferous	Areas of coniferous trees, or mixed coniferous and broadleaved trees where both comprise of approximately >20% of the tree canopy, Pines, firs, spruces and other coniferous trees making up forests, or gallery forests within 100m of major roads.	Natural
Woodlands: Deciduous	Beech, oak, birch, maple, and any other type of deciduous tree species making up forests, or gallery forests along roads, rivers, canals, etc.	Natural
Heath	Areas with low scrubby vegetation. Heath and moor land usually found in up-land areas, can be heather, coarse grass, bracken, or moss.	Natural
Wetlands	Wet meadows and low vegetation. Reed marshes, peat bogs, etc.	Natural
Agricultural: Orchards	Continuous areas with fruit trees.	Natural
Agricultural: Mixed	Areas of generally open fields, but with some sparsely distributed single mature trees or very small groups of trees. It may include small groups of trees on open land, garden, and parklands with trees. Tree cover density should not exceed about 30%.	Natural
Farm	Buildings used for Farming activities in rural areas, including one or two dwellings. Distinguished from small settlements and hamlets with multiple dwellings.	Human-built
Glasshouse	Large buildings consisting mainly of glass used for growing plants	Human-built
Recreational land	Recreational parks, sport fields, golf courses, camping and caravan sites, cemeteries, zoological and botanical gardens, typified by large areas of manicured grass land (not used for growing crops), with and without stands of trees.	Natural

Landscapes Have Distinct Emotion Profiles

Recreational building	Multi-functional large (generally greater the 60 × 100m) single or agglomerated building of multiple use and irregular shape and height, e.g., Airport terminals. Hospitals, Rail terminals, University campuses, exhibition halls and sports stadia.	Human-built
Residential: Low density	Smaller single or continuous buildings (typically family homes), typically of 1 or 2 storey height and with high percentage of vegetation (gardens). Areas made up of either small blocks of terraced house or semi-detached houses with gardens, normally situated outside the city centre are included in this category.	Human-built
Residential: Medium density	Larger single or continuous buildings between 3 and 5 storeys (approx. 10m to 18m), with some vegetation in between (e.g., apartment buildings). Usually included in this category would be post war local authority estates, usually at the edge of city centres and rows of terraced houses not more than 3 storeys high, usually with small gardens.	Human-built
Residential: High density	Continuous building rows, little vegetation, buildings having 3 or more storeys, typically found in city centres in big and mid-range cities can include dense residential areas with courtyard style gardens.	Human-built
Industrial: Business parks	Large areas of office accommodation often on the edge of towns or away from it, usually of modern construction. The class describes only the buildings and not parking areas.	Human-built
Industrial: Retail-park	Large retail areas often on the edge of towns typically of warehouse-style construction or purpose-built shopping centres. The class describes only the buildings and not parking areas.	Human-built
Industrial area	General industrial and utility sites and Industrial estates, including combinations of smaller business industrial units, distribution warehouses (approximately less than 100m dimensions), factory units (works and depots) and other similar buildings and the space between them. Also includes smaller sewerage works and other infrastructure sites.	Human-built
Railroads	Man-made concrete or tar based sealings of the plain ground, such as roads, parking areas, airport runways, etc. 2014 update will replace the minimum width criteria of 25m with variable road widths based on grade of road, e.g., Motorway, A	Human-built

Road, local street etc. Large parking areas around
business parks and retail sites fall in this category.

Table S2

Estimated Marginal Means for Emotion Intensity by Landscape, N = 48,943, Nppts= 192

Emotion	Estimated Marginal Means	Standard Error	Lower Confidence Interval	Upper Confidence Interval
Coast				
Nostalgic	0.919	0.072	0.778	1.060
Awe	1.029	0.072	0.889	1.170
Elated	0.988	0.072	0.847	1.129
Happy	1.048	0.072	0.907	1.189
Excited	0.964	0.072	0.823	1.105
Serene	1.041	0.072	0.901	1.182
Calm	1.061	0.072	0.920	1.202
Contented	1.042	0.072	0.901	1.183
Relaxed	1.071	0.072	0.930	1.212
Alert	0.055	0.072	-0.085	0.196
Bored	-0.739	0.072	-0.880	-0.598
Tense	-0.559	0.072	-0.700	-0.419
Nervous	-0.369	0.072	-0.509	-0.228
Upset	-0.336	0.072	-0.476	-0.195
Stressed	-0.567	0.072	-0.708	-0.427
Depressed	-0.435	0.072	-0.576	-0.295
Sad	-0.405	0.072	-0.545	-0.264
Woodlands: Coniferous				
Nostalgic	0.517	0.072	0.375	0.659
Awe	0.707	0.072	0.565	0.849
Elated	0.553	0.072	0.411	0.695
Happy	0.550	0.072	0.408	0.692
Excited	0.581	0.072	0.439	0.723
Serene	0.566	0.072	0.424	0.708
Calm	0.529	0.072	0.387	0.671
Contented	0.454	0.072	0.312	0.596
Relaxed	0.516	0.072	0.374	0.658
Alert	0.162	0.072	0.020	0.304
Bored	-0.646	0.072	-0.788	-0.504
Tense	-0.194	0.072	-0.336	-0.052
Nervous	-0.143	0.072	-0.285	-0.001
Upset	-0.165	0.072	-0.307	-0.023
Stressed	-0.295	0.072	-0.437	-0.153
Depressed	-0.365	0.072	-0.507	-0.223
Sad	-0.166	0.072	-0.308	-0.024
Woodlands: Deciduous				
Nostalgic	0.517	0.072	0.376	0.658
Awe	0.922	0.072	0.782	1.063

Landscapes Have Distinct Emotion Profiles

Elated	0.623	0.072	0.482	0.763
Happy	0.784	0.072	0.643	0.925
Excited	0.565	0.072	0.424	0.706
Serene	0.833	0.072	0.692	0.974
Calm	0.682	0.072	0.541	0.822
Contented	0.712	0.072	0.571	0.852
Relaxed	0.728	0.072	0.588	0.869
Alert	0.112	0.072	-0.028	0.253
Bored	-0.684	0.072	-0.824	-0.543
Tense	-0.366	0.072	-0.507	-0.225
Nervous	-0.266	0.072	-0.407	-0.126
Upset	-0.343	0.072	-0.484	-0.203
Stressed	-0.381	0.072	-0.522	-0.241
Depressed	-0.479	0.072	-0.620	-0.338
Sad	-0.357	0.072	-0.498	-0.216
Heath				
Nostalgic	0.115	0.072	-0.026	0.255
Awe	0.428	0.072	0.287	0.568
Elated	0.265	0.072	0.124	0.405
Happy	0.329	0.072	0.188	0.469
Excited	0.261	0.072	0.120	0.401
Serene	0.437	0.072	0.297	0.578
Calm	0.322	0.072	0.182	0.463
Contented	0.446	0.072	0.306	0.587
Relaxed	0.360	0.072	0.219	0.500
Alert	-0.036	0.072	-0.177	0.104
Bored	-0.290	0.072	-0.431	-0.149
Tense	-0.292	0.072	-0.433	-0.152
Nervous	-0.090	0.072	-0.231	0.050
Upset	-0.145	0.072	-0.286	-0.004
Stressed	-0.276	0.072	-0.417	-0.135
Depressed	-0.231	0.072	-0.372	-0.091
Sad	-0.201	0.072	-0.342	-0.060
Wetlands				
Nostalgic	0.056	0.072	-0.084	0.196
Awe	0.431	0.072	0.291	0.572
Elated	0.228	0.072	0.088	0.368
Happy	0.391	0.072	0.251	0.531
Excited	0.330	0.072	0.189	0.470
Serene	0.455	0.072	0.315	0.595
Calm	0.429	0.072	0.289	0.570
Contented	0.413	0.072	0.273	0.554
Relaxed	0.417	0.072	0.276	0.557
Alert	-0.150	0.072	-0.291	-0.010
Bored	-0.373	0.072	-0.514	-0.233
Tense	-0.234	0.072	-0.375	-0.094
Nervous	-0.252	0.072	-0.393	-0.112
Upset	-0.201	0.072	-0.342	-0.061
Stressed	-0.262	0.072	-0.402	-0.122
Depressed	-0.114	0.072	-0.254	0.027

Landscapes Have Distinct Emotion Profiles

Sad	-0.118	0.072	-0.258	0.022
Agricultural: Orchards				
Nostalgic	-0.019	0.071	-0.159	0.120
Awe	0.092	0.071	-0.048	0.231
Elated	0.031	0.071	-0.109	0.171
Happy	0.098	0.071	-0.042	0.237
Excited	0.037	0.071	-0.103	0.177
Serene	0.108	0.071	-0.032	0.247
Calm	0.017	0.071	-0.123	0.156
Contented	0.085	0.071	-0.055	0.225
Relaxed	0.050	0.071	-0.090	0.190
Alert	0.060	0.071	-0.080	0.200
Bored	-0.147	0.071	-0.286	-0.007
Tense	0.066	0.071	-0.074	0.206
Nervous	0.103	0.071	-0.036	0.243
Upset	0.081	0.071	-0.059	0.221
Stressed	0.028	0.071	-0.112	0.168
Depressed	0.006	0.071	-0.134	0.146
Sad	0.039	0.071	-0.101	0.179
Agricultural: Crops				
Nostalgic	0.313	0.072	0.172	0.453
Awe	0.367	0.072	0.226	0.508
Elated	0.336	0.072	0.195	0.476
Happy	0.477	0.072	0.336	0.617
Excited	0.278	0.072	0.137	0.418
Serene	0.571	0.072	0.430	0.712
Calm	0.540	0.072	0.399	0.680
Contented	0.487	0.072	0.347	0.628
Relaxed	0.562	0.072	0.421	0.702
Alert	-0.227	0.072	-0.368	-0.086
Bored	-0.333	0.072	-0.473	-0.192
Tense	-0.384	0.072	-0.525	-0.243
Nervous	-0.444	0.072	-0.585	-0.303
Upset	-0.329	0.072	-0.470	-0.189
Stressed	-0.440	0.072	-0.580	-0.299
Depressed	-0.362	0.072	-0.503	-0.222
Sad	-0.313	0.072	-0.453	-0.172
Agricultural: Mixed				
Nostalgic	0.357	0.072	0.217	0.498
Awe	0.331	0.072	0.191	0.471
Elated	0.271	0.072	0.131	0.411
Happy	0.330	0.072	0.190	0.471
Excited	0.206	0.072	0.066	0.346
Serene	0.457	0.072	0.317	0.597
Calm	0.510	0.072	0.370	0.650
Contented	0.422	0.072	0.281	0.562
Relaxed	0.492	0.072	0.352	0.633
Alert	-0.248	0.072	-0.388	-0.108
Bored	-0.262	0.072	-0.402	-0.121
Tense	-0.428	0.072	-0.568	-0.287

Landscapes Have Distinct Emotion Profiles

Nervous	-0.374	0.072	-0.515	-0.234
Upset	-0.277	0.072	-0.417	-0.136
Stressed	-0.474	0.072	-0.614	-0.334
Depressed	-0.366	0.072	-0.506	-0.226
Sad	-0.317	0.072	-0.458	-0.177
Farm				
Nostalgic	0.309	0.071	0.170	0.449
Awe	0.192	0.071	0.053	0.332
Elated	0.261	0.071	0.121	0.400
Happy	0.326	0.071	0.186	0.465
Excited	0.305	0.071	0.166	0.445
Serene	0.219	0.071	0.080	0.359
Calm	0.199	0.071	0.059	0.338
Contented	0.225	0.071	0.085	0.364
Relaxed	0.234	0.071	0.094	0.373
Alert	-0.015	0.071	-0.155	0.124
Bored	-0.310	0.071	-0.449	-0.171
Tense	-0.266	0.071	-0.406	-0.127
Nervous	-0.225	0.071	-0.364	-0.085
Upset	-0.226	0.071	-0.366	-0.087
Stressed	-0.310	0.071	-0.450	-0.171
Depressed	-0.268	0.071	-0.407	-0.129
Sad	-0.321	0.071	-0.461	-0.182
Glasshouse				
Nostalgic	-0.478	0.071	-0.617	-0.340
Awe	-0.327	0.071	-0.465	-0.188
Elated	-0.263	0.071	-0.402	-0.125
Happy	-0.385	0.071	-0.524	-0.247
Excited	-0.219	0.071	-0.357	-0.080
Serene	-0.397	0.071	-0.535	-0.258
Calm	-0.353	0.071	-0.492	-0.215
Contented	-0.386	0.071	-0.525	-0.247
Relaxed	-0.383	0.071	-0.522	-0.245
Alert	-0.178	0.071	-0.317	-0.040
Bored	0.346	0.071	0.207	0.484
Tense	0.026	0.071	-0.113	0.164
Nervous	0.022	0.071	-0.117	0.160
Upset	0.140	0.071	0.001	0.278
Stressed	-0.011	0.071	-0.150	0.128
Depressed	0.149	0.071	0.010	0.288
Sad	0.189	0.071	0.051	0.328
Recreational Land				
Nostalgic	0.340	0.070	0.202	0.477
Awe	0.178	0.070	0.040	0.316
Elated	0.245	0.070	0.107	0.382
Happy	0.248	0.070	0.110	0.386
Excited	0.146	0.070	0.009	0.284
Serene	0.295	0.070	0.157	0.433
Calm	0.314	0.070	0.176	0.452
Contented	0.246	0.070	0.108	0.384

Landscapes Have Distinct Emotion Profiles

Relaxed	0.330	0.070	0.192	0.468
Alert	-0.128	0.070	-0.266	0.010
Bored	-0.258	0.070	-0.396	-0.121
Tense	-0.250	0.070	-0.387	-0.112
Nervous	-0.145	0.070	-0.283	-0.008
Upset	-0.058	0.070	-0.196	0.080
Stressed	-0.177	0.070	-0.315	-0.039
Depressed	-0.208	0.070	-0.346	-0.070
Sad	-0.116	0.070	-0.254	0.022
Residential: Low density				
Nostalgic	0.212	0.072	0.071	0.352
Awe	-0.220	0.072	-0.361	-0.080
Elated	-0.002	0.072	-0.142	0.138
Happy	0.165	0.072	0.025	0.306
Excited	-0.116	0.072	-0.257	0.024
Serene	0.063	0.072	-0.077	0.204
Calm	0.185	0.072	0.044	0.325
Contented	0.174	0.072	0.034	0.314
Relaxed	0.170	0.072	0.030	0.311
Alert	-0.272	0.072	-0.412	-0.131
Bored	0.129	0.072	-0.012	0.269
Tense	-0.264	0.072	-0.405	-0.124
Nervous	-0.190	0.072	-0.330	-0.050
Upset	-0.214	0.072	-0.354	-0.074
Stressed	-0.239	0.072	-0.379	-0.099
Depressed	-0.328	0.072	-0.468	-0.187
Sad	-0.180	0.072	-0.320	-0.040
Residential: Medium density				
Nostalgic	-0.309	0.071	-0.449	-0.170
Awe	-0.545	0.071	-0.685	-0.406
Elated	-0.457	0.071	-0.596	-0.318
Happy	-0.563	0.071	-0.702	-0.423
Excited	-0.468	0.071	-0.608	-0.329
Serene	-0.536	0.071	-0.675	-0.396
Calm	-0.414	0.071	-0.554	-0.275
Contented	-0.499	0.071	-0.638	-0.359
Relaxed	-0.518	0.071	-0.658	-0.379
Alert	-0.265	0.071	-0.405	-0.126
Bored	0.471	0.071	0.332	0.611
Tense	0.045	0.071	-0.094	0.185
Nervous	-0.067	0.071	-0.207	0.072
Upset	0.167	0.071	0.027	0.306
Stressed	0.125	0.071	-0.015	0.264
Depressed	0.472	0.071	0.333	0.612
Sad	0.340	0.071	0.201	0.480
Residential: High density				
Nostalgic	-0.248	0.065	-0.376	-0.121
Awe	-0.455	0.065	-0.583	-0.328
Elated	-0.322	0.065	-0.450	-0.195
Happy	-0.360	0.065	-0.488	-0.233

Landscapes Have Distinct Emotion Profiles

Excited	-0.297	0.065	-0.425	-0.170
Serene	-0.456	0.065	-0.584	-0.329
Calm	-0.454	0.065	-0.582	-0.327
Contented	-0.407	0.065	-0.535	-0.280
Relaxed	-0.435	0.065	-0.562	-0.307
Alert	0.226	0.065	0.099	0.354
Bored	0.343	0.065	0.216	0.470
Tense	0.354	0.065	0.226	0.481
Nervous	0.357	0.065	0.229	0.484
Upset	0.195	0.065	0.068	0.323
Stressed	0.376	0.065	0.249	0.503
Depressed	0.278	0.065	0.150	0.405
Sad	0.206	0.065	0.079	0.334
Industry: Business Park				
Nostalgic	-0.657	0.070	-0.794	-0.520
Awe	-0.673	0.070	-0.810	-0.536
Elated	-0.598	0.070	-0.735	-0.461
Happy	-0.802	0.070	-0.939	-0.666
Excited	-0.624	0.070	-0.760	-0.487
Serene	-0.804	0.070	-0.941	-0.667
Calm	-0.706	0.070	-0.843	-0.569
Contented	-0.763	0.070	-0.900	-0.627
Relaxed	-0.763	0.070	-0.900	-0.627
Alert	-0.010	0.070	-0.147	0.126
Bored	0.701	0.070	0.565	0.838
Tense	0.502	0.070	0.366	0.639
Nervous	0.403	0.070	0.267	0.540
Upset	0.419	0.070	0.282	0.555
Stressed	0.488	0.070	0.351	0.625
Depressed	0.586	0.070	0.449	0.723
Sad	0.485	0.070	0.348	0.622
Industry: Retail Park				
Nostalgic	-0.433	0.081	-0.592	-0.274
Awe	-0.648	0.081	-0.807	-0.489
Elated	-0.519	0.081	-0.678	-0.360
Happy	-0.522	0.081	-0.681	-0.363
Excited	-0.401	0.081	-0.560	-0.242
Serene	-0.721	0.081	-0.880	-0.562
Calm	-0.700	0.081	-0.859	-0.541
Contented	-0.603	0.081	-0.762	-0.444
Relaxed	-0.585	0.081	-0.744	-0.426
Alert	0.249	0.081	0.090	0.408
Bored	0.507	0.081	0.347	0.666
Tense	0.590	0.081	0.431	0.749
Nervous	0.408	0.081	0.249	0.567
Upset	0.218	0.081	0.059	0.377
Stressed	0.650	0.081	0.491	0.810
Depressed	0.270	0.081	0.111	0.429
Sad	0.249	0.081	0.090	0.408
Industry: Industrial Area				

Landscapes Have Distinct Emotion Profiles

Nostalgic	-0.559	0.070	-0.696	-0.421
Awe	-0.681	0.070	-0.818	-0.544
Elated	-0.629	0.070	-0.766	-0.492
Happy	-0.779	0.070	-0.917	-0.642
Excited	-0.611	0.070	-0.748	-0.473
Serene	-0.787	0.070	-0.924	-0.650
Calm	-0.794	0.070	-0.931	-0.657
Contented	-0.766	0.070	-0.903	-0.629
Relaxed	-0.787	0.070	-0.924	-0.650
Alert	0.091	0.070	-0.046	0.228
Bored	0.700	0.070	0.562	0.837
Tense	0.494	0.070	0.357	0.631
Nervous	0.368	0.070	0.231	0.505
Upset	0.438	0.070	0.301	0.575
Stressed	0.638	0.070	0.501	0.775
Depressed	0.569	0.070	0.432	0.706
Sad	0.396	0.070	0.259	0.534
Recreational Building				
Nostalgic	-0.622	0.082	-0.783	-0.461
Awe	-0.657	0.082	-0.817	-0.496
Elated	-0.688	0.082	-0.849	-0.527
Happy	-0.919	0.082	-1.080	-0.758
Excited	-0.713	0.082	-0.874	-0.552
Serene	-0.881	0.082	-1.042	-0.720
Calm	-0.863	0.082	-1.024	-0.702
Contented	-0.841	0.082	-1.002	-0.680
Relaxed	-0.910	0.082	-1.071	-0.749
Alert	0.136	0.082	-0.025	0.297
Bored	0.625	0.082	0.464	0.786
Tense	0.753	0.082	0.592	0.914
Nervous	0.502	0.082	0.341	0.663
Upset	0.599	0.082	0.438	0.760
Stressed	0.647	0.082	0.486	0.808
Depressed	0.709	0.082	0.548	0.870
Sad	0.554	0.082	0.393	0.715
Railroads				
Nostalgic	-0.423	0.070	-0.561	-0.286
Awe	-0.549	0.070	-0.686	-0.411
Elated	-0.432	0.070	-0.570	-0.295
Happy	-0.548	0.070	-0.685	-0.410
Excited	-0.323	0.070	-0.461	-0.186
Serene	-0.606	0.070	-0.744	-0.469
Calm	-0.644	0.070	-0.782	-0.507
Contented	-0.565	0.070	-0.703	-0.428
Relaxed	-0.675	0.070	-0.812	-0.537
Alert	0.471	0.070	0.333	0.608
Bored	0.301	0.070	0.163	0.438
Tense	0.577	0.070	0.440	0.715
Nervous	0.480	0.070	0.343	0.618
Upset	0.134	0.070	-0.003	0.272

Landscapes Have Distinct Emotion Profiles

Stressed	0.617	0.070	0.480	0.755
Depressed	0.209	0.070	0.071	0.346
Sad	0.123	0.070	-0.015	0.260